

Sn-CATALYSIS AS AN EFFICIENT DEPOLYMERIZATION STEP OF POLY(LACTIDE) TO LACTIDE

Klementina Pušnik Črešnar, Irena Pulko

Faculty of polymer technology, Slovenia

Professional paper

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10008164

klementina.pusnik@ftpo.eu

Abstract: *Increasing the high-performance quality of recycled material, accelerating the renewable raw material and renewable energy, production technologies, renewable material addressing the non-toxic chemical with the generation of minimised waste; and secondly, improving the green way of producing plastic material are the main Economy Strategy plan. In this context, plastics made from renewable resources have advantages over fossil-based plastics and provide benefits to the circular economy. Therefore, the chemical recycling of renewable resources such as poly(lactide) (PLA) could be a beneficial approach to ensure the high quality of the produced material (monomer) and to add benefits to a circular economy. In this context, PLA-based plastics have been investigated. Due to its bio-based and renewable nature, PLA has been expanded in many applications such as packaging, biopharmaceutics, drug delivery carriers, 3D printing devices. In this context, many different types of chemical recycling based on depolymerisation have been developed, where the conversion of the end-of-life polymer into useful molecular weight compounds is crucial. The lactide obtained by chemical recycling is subjected to ring-opening polymerisation accompanied by catalysis to obtain high molecular weight PLA.*

In addition, the catalytic depolymerisation of PLA to lactide was investigated. In the literature, many salts have been used as catalysts for the depolymerisation of PLA. In our study, the depolymerisation step of PLA was investigated by varying the depolymerisation conditions such as concentration of tin salts as catalysts, time of depolymerisation and the potential of Sn(OAc)₂ as a catalyst in the depolymerisation of PLA has been demonstrated so far. The results of Sn-catalysed depolymerisation of PLA to obtain lactide, characterised by DSC, ATR-

FTIR and TGA methods, showed the presence of yields at 220°C (6 mbar) within 4 hours.

Keywords: poly(lactide) (PLA), chemical recycling, catalysis, Sn(OOct)₂

1 INTRODUCTION

The vision of Europe outlined in the European Circular Economy Strategy and the European Green Deal fully respects the concept of reuse, recycling and durability (European Commission, 2018b). Environmental concerns are increasing, and environmental legislation is becoming more stringent. Therefore, there is a trend towards research biodegradable polymer materials that could become alternatives to non-degradable fossil-based polymers. On the one hand, to increase the high-performance quality of recycled materials to address the generation of minimised amount of waste; and on the other hand, to improve the environmentally friendly way in which plastic materials are produced (European Commission, 2018a)(Hatti-Kaul, Nilsson, Zhang, Rehnberg, & Lundmark, 2020).

Plastics made from renewable resources have advantages over fossil-based plastics and offer benefits for the circular economy. A number of biodegradable polymers are already on the market (Chinaglia, Tosin, & Degli-innocenti, 2018; Mostafa & Tayeb, 2018; Shruti & Kutralam-Muniasamy, 2019). The most widely used material is polylactic acid (PLA) (Araújo, Oliveira, Oliveira, Botelho, & Machado, 2014). PLA, an aliphatic thermoplastic polyester derived from renewable resources such as corn starch, potatoes and sugarcane, is recognised as a bio-based and renewable polymer that is an alternative to petrochemical-based polymers (Ramot, Haim-Zada, Domb, & Nyska, 2016). The thermoplastic polyester has already been used in various applications, bioengineering (drug delivery, tissue engineering, 3D printed devices) and biochemistry, as well as for food packaging (Bang & Kim, 2012; Othman, 2014; Zhong, Godwin, Jin, & Xiao, 2020). The most effective way to synthesise PLA is the well-known ring-opening polymerisation of lactide, which is formed from lactic acid, a product of the fermentation of agricultural compounds, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 7. Synthesis of PLA; ring opening polymerization of lactide formed by lactic acid.

From an environmental point of view, the most important role of PLA is proper disposal, followed by recycling. Broadly speaking, there are two types of recycling, mechanical and chemical (Manufacturers, 2020; Mercante et al., 2018). Chemical recycling of renewable resources such as PLA could be a beneficial approach to ensure the high quality of the produced material (monomer) and contribute to a circular economy. The main challenge is proper disposal of the waste, followed by recycling to produce new materials. Many recycling techniques have been explored with varying degrees of success, as different recycling techniques release gases into the air that cause pollution. One of the most successful recycling techniques is chemical recycling through depolymerisation, where the recovered plastic is returned to its raw state and the polymer can then be resynthesised.

Chemical recycling of PLA involves a range of advanced recycling technologies that convert plastic waste into raw materials for the chemical industry, such as monomers, oligomers and hydrocarbons. These raw materials can be used to produce plastics without any degradation in quality and without any restrictions on the type of use. Several chemical recycling technologies are currently being developed and investigated, including depolymerisation, gasification and hydrocracking. Depolymerisation of PLA can take the form of pyrolysis, which yields a lactide product, and hydrolysis and alcoholysis, which yield lactic acid or other chemicals as products (Figure 2) (Abe, Takahashi, Kim, Mochizuki, & Doi, 2004).

Figure 8. Recycling of PLA (McKeown & Jones, 2020).

The synthesis of valuable chemicals that would otherwise be lost as CO_2 (in incineration or composting) and the ability to synthesise new PLA with desired mechanical properties are the main advantages of chemical recycling over composting and mechanical recycling. Studies have shown that the production of lactic acid *D*-lysine by chemical depolymerisation is more energy efficient than the production of virgin material by the expensive fermentation route. An additional advantage of chemical recycling methods is that the process can be resistant to contamination by other plastics, reducing the need for costly segregation (Piemonte, Sabatini, & Gironi, 2013).

One of the chemical recycling methods is therefore the depolymerisation of PLA into a lactide product, which could be reused as a raw material for the production of PLA. The scheme of polymerisation and depolymerisation is shown in Figure 3, from which it can be seen that depolymerisation requires a suitable catalyst. The most commonly used catalysts that can be used for the depolymerisation of PLA to obtain lactide are zinc and tin based, such as $\text{Zn}(\text{OAc})_2$ and $\text{Sn}(\text{Oct})_2$.

Figure 9. Polymerization and depolymerization step of PLA.

Lactide is a cyclic lactone ester with the molecular formula $C_6H_8O_4$. It is formed by the esterification of two or more molecules of lactic acid or another suitable hydroxycarboxylic acid. As mentioned above, lactic acid exists in a number of stereoisomeric structures, and so does lactide. L-lactide, D-lactide and mesolactide are known (Figure 3). All forms of lactide are transparent or off-white. The molecular weight of lactide is 144.13 g/mol and the melting point is between 95°C and 97°C.

Tin (II) 2-ethylhexanoate or tin octoate ($Sn(Oct)_2$), ($C_{16}H_{30}O_4Sn$) is a compound formed by the reaction of stannous oxide and 2-ethylhexanoic acid. It is a colourless liquid at room temperature, but often appears yellow due to impurities resulting from oxidation. Tin octoate has a molecular weight of 405.12 g/mol and a density of 1.251 g/cm³. It is most commonly used as a catalyst for the polymerisation of various monomers, but in several studies, it has been used with zinc octoate as a depolymerisation catalyst in chemical recycling processes.

Prior to the synthesis of recycled lactide from PLA, which will be reported in a later chapter, we present here the preliminary study on the chemical recycling step of PLA using tin-based catalysts, $Sn(Oct)_2$. This is a novel investigation with respect to PLA and catalysts and involves the sum of the following complementary techniques: Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) and Thermal Gravimetric Analysis (TGA). The data are analysed and evaluated.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

The depolymerization reaction conditions of PLA were studied using two commercially available test samples designated as PLA 3002D (PLA1) and PLA P400 (PLA2) (Table 1). The depolymerisation reaction of PLA as the main component was studied by varying the mass of PLA added and the concentration of catalysts $Sn(Oct)_2$ (Table 1).

Table 1. Depolimerization reaction condition of PLA.

Sample abbreviation	PLA	Mass of PLA (g)	Concent. of catalysts (mol. %)
PLA2-1	PLA2	20	0,2
PLA1-1	PLA1	20	0,2
PLA2-2	PLA2	20	0,4
PLA1-2	PLA1	20	0,4
PLA2-3	PLA2	20	1
PLA1-3	PLA1	20	1

Samples of PLA and catalyst $\text{Sn}(\text{Oct})_2$ were first added to the flask. Glassware for the reaction was set up and the reaction mixture was heated under vacuum with stirring. For each sample, the flask containing the PLA was weighed, an appropriate volume of catalyst was added, and the flask was fitted with a magnetic stirrer and placed in a sand bath. During the process, the PLA melted and liquefied. The condenser was used to cool and crystallise the lactide.

Figure 10. Product of PLA depolimerization.

The presence of the depolimerisation product, assumed to be L-lactide, was characterised by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (ATR-FTIR) and thermal gravimetric analysis (TGA).

DSC was used to evaluate the neat PLA reference material and the presence of L-lactide. Firstly, neat, depolymerised PLA was measured in the temperature range 25-200 °C in a high purity nitrogen atmosphere using a Mettler Toledo DSC 2 calibrated with indium for temperature and enthalpy and sapphire for heat capacity. Measurements were performed on samples of ~10-20 mg mass sealed in aluminium pans. A first heating scan up to 200 °C was performed to erase the thermal history and then the next main thermal protocols were applied as follows: standard cooling and heating at 10 K/min. Secondly, the L-lactide products of the prepared samples were tested in a nitrogen (N_2) atmosphere at a nitrogen flow rate of 20 mL/min and a temperature range of 25°C to 100°C, with a heating rate of 5°C/min. As we were only interested in the melting point

of the lactide, the samples were heated and cooled only once. ATR-FTIR spectra were monitored on a Perker Elmer, Spectrum 65. The spectra were recorded in the wavenumber range from 600 to 4000 cm^{-1} at room temperature (RT). Each spectrum was determined as an average of 32 scans at a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} for measuring background. All spectra presented here were baseline corrected and smoothed upon the measurement.

The thermodynamic properties of the neat PLA and the lactide products of the prepared samples were determined by TGA analysis on a Mettler Toledo TGA/DSC 3+ using 40 μL crucible. All samples were tested under heating in a nitrogen (N_2) atmosphere at a flow rate of 20 mL/min and a temperature range of 25°C to 550°C at a heating rate of 10°C/min. When the temperature reached 550°C, the samples were heated for a further 10 minutes in an oxygen (O_2) atmosphere at a flow rate of 20 mL/min.

3. RESULTS

The depolymerisation products were obtained from different PLA virgin material (Table 2). By comparing the weight of products with different depolymerisation time, the formation of lactide is assumed to be the main product.

Comparing the performance of samples PLA2-1, PLA1-1, PLA2-3 and PLA1-3, it can be seen that the amount of catalyst affected both the amount of lactide extracted and the rate of lactide formation itself. The type of PLA material itself did not have a major influence on the depolymerisation, as a comparable amount of lactide was obtained in the same depolymerisation time in both cases (18.69 g for sample PLA2-3 and 17.61 g for sample PLA1-3).

Table 2. Depolymerization product.

Sample	Lactide weight [g]	mass [wt.%]	Depolymerization time [h]
PLA2-1	7,43	37	2,5
PLA1-1	11,62	58	4
PLA2-2	1,79	9	3
PLA1-2	2,57	13	3
PLA2-3	18,69	93,5	2,5
PLA1-3	17,61	88	2,5

In Figure5, the spectra by ATR-FTIR are shown for all samples, including the PLA 3002D (PLA1) and PLA P400 (PLA2). The results of characteristics vibration band are in accordance with previous works on neat PLA. The absorption peaks between 2900-3000 cm^{-1} correspond to symmetric and asymmetric C-H bond stretching of the CH_3 group. The absorption peak between 1745-1750 cm^{-1} is

related to vibrations of the C=O bond due to the presence of the ester group. The peak between 1450-1455 cm^{-1} is characteristic of asymmetric vibrations of the CH_3 group bending. The absorption peak between 1357-1359 cm^{-1} corresponds to the bending vibration of the C-O-H group. The peak at 1267 cm^{-1} is related to the C=O double bond bending vibration and the peaks between 1181-1182 cm^{-1} correspond to the C-O-C stretching vibration of the ester groups (Črešnar, Aulova, et al., 2021; Črešnar, Klonos, et al., 2021).

Figure 11. Characteristic vibration of neat PLA needed for depolymerization reaction in the wavenumber from 500 to 4000 cm^{-1} .

The ATR-FTIR spectra of the PLA depolymerization product samples are compared in Figure 6. The ATR-FTIR spectra of the lactide samples (Figure 6) showed the similar characteristic peaks between 2900-3000 cm^{-1} corresponding to symmetric and asymmetric vibrations of the C-H bond of the CH_3 group. Peaks observed in the range of 1750-1753 cm^{-1} where pronounced by the vibration of the C=O double bond occurs in the cyclic dilactone. The absorption peak between 1440-1460 cm^{-1} and the absorption peak at 1380 cm^{-1} correspond to symmetric and asymmetric bending vibrations of the C-H bond of the CH_3 group. The peak at 1265-1266 cm^{-1} corresponds to asymmetric vibrations of the C-O-C bond in the lactone ring and the peak at 1094-1095 cm^{-1} corresponds to symmetric vibrations of the C-O-C bond in the lactone ring (Nikolic et al., 2010).

Figure 12. ATR-FTIR spectra of lactide samples in the wavelength from 500 to 4000 cm^{-1}

The melting points of the PLA materials and all depolymerization products were determined by differential scanning calorimetry analysis. Figures 7 and 8 below show the thermograms of the neat PLA and the lactide product samples (PLA2-1, PLA1-1, PLA2-3 and PLA1-3).

Figure 13. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) thermogram of neat PLA.

Figure 14. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) thermograms lactide.

It can be seen that the melting points obtained for neat PLA and lactide are reasonable, as neat PLA has a melting point between 150 and 200°C (Tarani et al., 2021) and lactide around 95°C. A T_m of 166.6°C and a T_g of 58.8°C were measured for PLA1, while a T_m of 150.9°C and a T_g of 58.4°C were measured for PLA2. In the case of PLA2, crystallisation can also be observed, measured at 119.5°C. Both samples were measured in segment 6 during the second heating. The lactide of sample 1 has a T_m of 95.9°C, the lactide of sample 2 at 91.1°C and the lactide of sample 5 at 93.6°C. A slight deviation is observed for sample 6, where the melting point drops below 90°C to 89.2°C. These curves have also been measured in the heating segment, that is in segment 2.

3 CONCLUSIONS

In summary, an easy-to-adopt chemical recycling method of two commercial PLAs has been established. The depolymerisation of PLA by pyrolysis, where the product of the lactide monomer was obtained by chemical reaction. More specifically, the method was focused on the tin-catalysed ($\text{Sn}(\text{Oct})_2$), at 260°C and at a pressure of 6 mbar, depolymerisation of PLA to obtain lactide as depolymerisation product, which is an industrially relevant precursor for neat PLA.

The results also demonstrated the influence of catalysts on the depolymerisation time. It was shown that L-lactide depolymerised faster as the number of catalysts increased. The successful depolymerisation step of neat PLA was revealed by the

characteristic vibration band assigned to L-lactide and the temperature of the melting point T_m of L-lactide, which was found to be around 95°C including all depolymerisation product types.

Acknowledgments: *We would like to thank Maruša Dolinšek from Faculty of Polymer Technology for all laboratory support work and Lara Gosak for characterization of material.*

4 REFERENCES

Abe, H., Takahashi, N., Kim, K. J., Mochizuki, M., & Doi, Y. (2004). Thermal degradation processes of end-capped poly(L-lactide)s in the presence and absence of residual zinc catalyst. *Biomacromolecules*, 5(4), 1606–1614. <https://doi.org/10.1021/bm0497872>

Araújo, A., Oliveira, M., Oliveira, R., Botelho, G., & Machado, A. V. (2014). Biodegradation assessment of PLA and its nanocomposites. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 21(16), 9477–9486. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-013-2256-y>

Bang, G., & Kim, S. W. (2012). Biodegradable poly(lactic acid)-based hybrid coating materials for food packaging films with gas barrier properties. *Journal of Industrial and Engineering Chemistry*, 18(3), 1063–1068. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jiec.2011.12.004>

Chinaglia, S., Tosin, M., & Degli-innocenti, F. (2018). Biodegradation rate of biodegradable plastics at molecular level. *Polymer Degradation and Stability*, 147(December 2017), 237–244. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymdegradstab.2017.12.011>

Črešnar, K. P., Aulova, A., Bikiaris, D. N., Lambropoulou, D., Kuzmič, K., & Zemljič, L. F. (2021). Incorporation of metal-based nanoadditives into the pla matrix: Effect of surface properties on antibacterial activity and mechanical performance of pla nanoadditive films. *Molecules*, 26(14). <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules26144161>

Črešnar, K. P., Klonos, P. A., Zamboulis, A., Terzopoulou, Z., Xanthopoulou, E., Papadopoulos, L., ... Bikiaris, D. N. (2021). Structure-Properties relationships in renewable composites based on polylactide filled with Tannin and Kraft Lignin - Crystallization and molecular mobility. *Thermochimica Acta*, 703(June). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tca.2021.178998>

European Commission. (2018a). A European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy. COM(2018) 28 Final, SWD(2018)(1), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.7b02368>

European Commission. (2018b). A plastics strategy to protect Europe's citizens and the environment. Joint Research Centre European Commission, (2017), 1–2. Retrieved from https://ec.europa.eu/commission/sites/beta-political/files/plastics-factsheet-people-environment_en.pdf

Hatti-Kaul, R., Nilsson, L. J., Zhang, B., Rehnberg, N., & Lundmark, S. (2020). Designing Biobased Recyclable Polymers for Plastics. *Trends in Biotechnology*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tibtech.2019.04.011>

Manufacturers, P.-A. of plastics. (2020). Rethinking Packaging : An overview of the key principles that should guide the revision of the Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive and the Essential Requirements for packaging. 5.

McKeown, P., & Jones, M. D. (2020). The Chemical Recycling of PLA: A Review. *Sustainable Chemistry*, 1(1), 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.3390/suschem1010001>

Mercante, I., Alejandrino, C., Ojeda, J. P., Chini, J., Maroto, C., & Fajardo, N. (2018). Mortar and concrete composites with recycled plastic: A review. *Science and Technology of Materials*, 30, 69–79. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.stmat.2018.11.003>

Mostafa, N. A., & Tayeb, A. M. (2018). Production of biodegradable plastic from agricultural wastes. *Arabian Journal of Chemistry*, 11(4), 546–553. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.arabjc.2015.04.008>

Nikolic, L., Ristic, I., Adnadjevic, B., Nikolic, V., Jovanovic, J., & Stankovic, M. (2010). Novel microwave-assisted synthesis of poly(D,L-lactide): The influence of monomer/initiator molar ratio on the product properties. *Sensors*, 10(5), 5063–5073. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s100505063>

Othman, S. H. (2014). Bio-nanocomposite Materials for Food Packaging Applications: Types of Biopolymer and Nano-sized Filler. *Agriculture and Agricultural Science Procedia*, 2, 296–303. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aaspro.2014.11.042>

Piemonte, V., Sabatini, S., & Gironi, F. (2013). Chemical Recycling of PLA: A Great Opportunity Towards the Sustainable Development? *Journal of Polymers and the Environment*, 21(3), 640–647. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10924-013-0608-9>

Ramot, Y., Haim-Zada, M., Domb, A. J., & Nyska, A. (2016). Biocompatibility and safety of PLA and its copolymers. *Advanced Drug Delivery Reviews*, 107, 153–162. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addr.2016.03.012>

Shruti, V. C., & Kutralam-Muniasamy, G. (2019). Bioplastics: Missing link in the era of Microplastics. *Science of the Total Environment*, 697, 134139. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.134139>

Tarani, E., Pušnik Črešnar, K., Zemljič, L. F., Chrissafis, K., Papageorgiou, G. Z., Lambropoulou, D., ... Terzopoulou, Z. (2021). Cold crystallization kinetics and thermal degradation of pla composites with metal oxide nanofillers. *Applied Sciences (Switzerland)*, 11(7). <https://doi.org/10.3390/app11073004>

Zhong, Y., Godwin, P., Jin, Y., & Xiao, H. (2020). Biodegradable polymers and green-based antimicrobial packaging materials: A mini-review. *Advanced Industrial and Engineering Polymer Research*, 3(1), 27–35. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aiepr.2019.11.002>